

IMPROVEMENT OF THE URBAN ENVIRONMENT.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7110084>

Abstract

Currently, the processes of development and expansion of cities are increasingly observed. According to the UN, by 2030, more than 60% of the population will live in cities. The increase in the population living in cities has a negative impact on flora and fauna, changes in the natural landscape, environmental pollution, and the impact on air and water quality. The development of urbanization occurs under the extensive expansion of urban areas, densification of residential development, increased economic and social growth.

Keywords:

Physical well-being of residents, pedestrian accessibility, housing distribution, social, business and recreational infrastructure, urban ecosystem. The cities of the future presuppose the availability of comfortable housing, accessibility and diversity of trade and services, education, recreation, leisure and healthcare. To create agreements for the physical well-being of residents, their self-realization, self-development and productive interaction. In preserving the cultural heritage of future generations, multifunctional development is important. To do this, we must combine objects of trade and services, recreation and leisure, education and healthcare, offices and small industries. Pedestrian accessibility requires an even distribution of housing, social, business and recreational infrastructure. To organize workplaces, it is necessary to expand the range of services of daily and periodic demand. It is also fundamentally important to include offices and small industries in the residential development: an urban environment is created where "everything is at hand". For self-realization and development of the population, free up time for rest and leisure by reducing traffic congestion and comfort of urban roads. For representatives of the older generation, pedestrian accessibility helps to improve their health, gives them the opportunity to shop independently and get medical help near home. The priority of pedestrian accessibility encourages the growth of small businesses and attracts visitors from other parts of the city. As a consequence, the flow of people on this territory provides security at any time of the day: on foot, by public transport and in a car. This increases the territorial accessibility spent on moving around the city. Pedestrian flows in combination between sites and buildings increase the variety of routes of the street road network. To get to

your destination, intersections are placed at shorter intervals. To increase the reliability and safety of pedestrian movement, bicycle paths and public transport lanes are used.

For a quick and economical trip to work, study, recreation and leisure, the development of public transport, which has a large capacity, is of great importance. A competent urban ecosystem as a whole depends on the location of the urban environment, is a condition of the urban ecosystem as a whole. To enhance the resilience of urban design, develop policy guidelines for planners aimed at promoting informed, evidence-based intervention. This, in turn, will help to change the appearance of the landscape, existing cities, and in the design of new ones. The survey revealed a development that is at the stage of formation, both in theory and in practice.

The main task remains to consider the possibilities of each of the factors with the help of certain indicators formulated to take into account the diverse levels of the urban structure. This would open up new scenarios for the evaluation and subsequent monitoring of urban development projects. This work is only a partial contribution to the efforts to develop a new alignment. It gives an impetus to the design of resilient urban forms, as well as to the quantitative and better monitoring of our cities.

The paper also examines the impact of the development of large urban agglomerations on well-being and quality of life. The attractiveness of megacities from the standpoint of increasing urbanization, the concentration of investment resources and the accumulation of industrial, financial and business centers in them today does not unambiguously affect the well-being and comfort of human habitation. The conversion of the accumulated "wealth" of the metropolis into an attractive environment for living becomes an elusive problem that requires the study of the main factors and parameters of comfortable urban living. The methodology presented in the paper for assessing megacities according to the formed parameters of the comfort of the urban environment allows us to identify the areas of necessary improvement.

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